

fast and slow practice

A visual essay of our design methodology in scenography and architecture

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'fast and slow practice' is a visual essay presented by Felix Schiettecatte, Lennart Vandewaetere, and Marius Vaneekhoutte, upon direct invitation by the editors, and was not peer-reviewed. The following documents are part of the contribution presented at the Practice in Research conference held at CIVA&ULB in March 2023.

“Hush Hush Stage, Contrair Open air 2019

The idea grew out of the Port of Antwerp, more specific the dry dock which is located next to the site. This unique construction allows the water level to be controlled and boats can be maneuvered. As the water pours into the dry dock, dancing people stream in to the Hush Hush stage. The visitors are enclosed along either side by dance platforms, which seek tension with the crown of the existing row of trees. Physically enclosing the place creates an intimate club atmosphere. The DJ booth is located in the heart of this ‘tub’ and is integrated under a staircase construction that functions as a meeting place in the treetops near the main entrance to the site.

Festival site, Noordkasteel Antwerp

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1. first idea sketch
2. sketch of a podium idea
3. plan/section of possible layering of the stage
4. perspective sketch inner atmosphere
5. idea for lighting system
6. section with measurements
7. layering structure ideas
8. drawing of the DJ-booth
9. section with measurements
10. section with measurements and DJ-booth
11. segment section with light concept
12. segment section
13. segment section
14. concept plan
15. introduction of the staircase
16. atmosphere sketch
17. model 1/50 lightning test
18. model 1/50 testing with scale figures
19. model 1/50 plan formation
20. model 1/50 outside façade
21. axonometric drawing, 3D-model V1
22. exterior rendering, 3D-model V1
23. exterior rendering, 3D-model V1
24. plan, 3D-model V1
25. exterior rendering, 3D-model V2
26. segment section, 3D-model V2
27. axonometric drawing, staircase, 3D-model V2
28. exterior rendering, 3D-model V3
29. exterior rendering, 3D-model V3
30. plan, 3D-model V3, final adjustments
31. contractor drawing, Allscaff scaffolding
32. exterior rendering, 3D-model V3

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Final design, axonometric drawing

Contrair Open Air, June 2019,
photo by Marius Vaneeckhoutte

Contrair Open Air, June 2019,
photo by Marius Vaneckhoutte

Contrair Open Air, June 2019,
photo by Marius Vaneckhoutte

Contrair Open Air, June 2019,
photo by Marius Vaneeckhoutte

Contrair Open Air, June 2019,
photo by Marius Vaneckhoutte

Contrair Open Air, June 2019,
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Contrair Open Air, June 2019,
photos by Contrair

“Berchem”, Renovation of a house 2020-2022

The project started by understanding and decomposing the house in its materiality and structure. Our goal was to strengthen – or perhaps merely support- the identity of the place through an addition or elimination. The house is solid and spacious, but the living room areas are lacking natural light and visual connection to the garden. Our main addition was the introduction of a ‘concrete table’, which supports the valuable bathroom volume on the first floor and allows us to eliminate the volumes underneath. This action created an opportunity to reorganize the spaces on the ground floor and allowed us to create a sequence of four rooms. This sequence creates a feeling of togetherness for the residents and allows light all the way through out the groundfloor plan.

Project as found, 2020

photo by Marius Vaneekhoutte

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final design plan

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Hopper Edward

House to design sketch

Model Anderson
(bring kitone)

REFERENCE, Edward Hopper, 7A.M. 1948

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L-profielen die koepel dragen
zijn meer een kef dan de sferen onder
de koepel.

REFERENCE, Winter garden, Ursuline Institute, Mechelen

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1. first idea of opening up to the garden
2. concept drawing of a concrete table
3. roof detail inspired by Edward Hopper
4. roof detail alligned with the concrete table
5. elevation sketch
6. elevation fragment drawing 1/10
7. window joint drawing 1/1
8. interior perspective sketch
9. detail fragments of the gutter system
10. skylight detaillling 1/50
11. skylight elevation drawing 1/10
12. back elevation 1/10
13. perspective drawing final desing
14. perspective detail drawing final design
15. interior perspective drawing final design
16. exterior perspective drawing final design
17. model 1/50 pre-design 1
18. model 1/50 pre-design 2 fragment
19. 3D model pre-design 2 section
20. model 1/50 pre-design 1
21. 3D model pre-design 2
22. axonometric drawing, urban planning check-up
23. model 1/50, pre-design 3
24. model 1/50, interior light experiment
25. model 1/50, concrete table vs. skylight
26. model 1/50, pre-design 3
27. 3d model exterior, building permit fase
28. model, building permit fase
29. 3d model interior, building permit fase
30. 3D-model tendering fase, interior research
31. model tendering fase, exterior
32. model tendering fase, interior

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Tendering fase, model 1/33

Tendering fase, model 1/33

construction site, 2021

construction site, 2021

construction site, 2021

construction site, 2021

construction site, 2021

Final result, summer 2022

Final result, summer 2022

Final result, summer 2022

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